

NDAC/LO/029

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Overview and computing requirements for the Step 2/3-process

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1. Introduction

The goal of the Step 2/3-solution process is the transformation of about $4 \cdot 10^6$ abscissa observations from the set solutions (Step 1) into about 2000 set zero points, about $5 \cdot 10^5$ astrometric parameters and a small (< 100) number of global distortion parameters. In the original Step 2, the zero-points were to be obtained from a small group of selected (PRS) stars, and then the astrometric parameters for all program stars were to be solved for in Step 3. The present concept (NDAC/LO/020) is to make the solution depend on as many stars as practicable, excluding only those with obvious complications (binaries etc). Also, by "preadjusting" the astrometric parameters during their elimination from the zero-point solution, Step 3 is actually included in what is properly called the Step 2/3-process. The algorithms for this task are given by Lindegren in WP6100, 7100 (NDAC/LO/021, 022), and the present note serves only to give some concrete estimates of the amounts of data and computations involved.

The input and output from the process are described by the DID:s in WP6100, 7100. In short, we have a main input of set solution data (DID33), and a main output of the astrometric results (DID37). The original set-solution data have to be sorted star-wise, and this is best done before the Step 2/3-process proper. The set results are stored on a few ($\lesssim 5$) magnetic tapes, and the sorting is easy if a separate file is available with the number of observations (sets) for each star. A disk file can then be economically dimensioned, and the tapes need be read through only once. The disk file can be used immediately or it can be saved again on tape. The other input data (star-catalogue, ephemerides, RGC-coordinates) are directly available on permanent disk files.

The Step 2/3-process is run several times in the course of the reductions, mostly with fewer than the total number of stars and observations. In the sequel, the maximum size of the task is assumed, and one should be aware that "typical" runs are less demanding.

2. Formation of the observation equations

An observation equation for star i in set j has the form

$$\sum_{k=1}^5 A_{ij}^{(k)} \Delta a_i^{(k)} - \Delta c_j + \sum_{k=1}^{NGLOB} G_{ij}^{(k)} \Delta g^{(k)} = U_{ij}^{obs} - U_{ij}^{comp} \quad (1)$$

Here $\Delta a_i^{(k)}$ are the corrections to the five astrometric parameters for star i , Δc_j is the correction to the abscissa zero-point for set j , and $\Delta g^{(k)}$ are the corrections to the global distortion parameters. The rhs are the differences between the observed and computed abscissae. The data and formulae required to set up each observation equation are given in the WP6100 definition (NDAC/LO/021), and the following sequence of steps serves only to make the process more explicit.

We assume first that the following data are available in auxiliary files:

- (a) $\sin \alpha_r$, $\cos \alpha_r$, $\sin \delta_r$, $\cos \delta_r$ and their products ("RGC-file")
- (b) α_o , δ_o , μ_α , μ_δ , Π , $\Pi v_R R^{-1}$ (star catalogue, updated version in separate file)
- (c) ROBS(1:3) and RSUN(1:3) (to be interpolated for $t = \text{TOBS}$ from data in a small "ephemeris file")

For each star (i) we have the primary input data j (set no), TOBS, ABSC (observed abscissa from set solution). The observation equation coefficients are formed using formulae (021.2-12), and the amount of computation required can be summarized as follows (with 1 op = 1 floating point addition, subtraction, multiplication, or division):

- 2.1. For computing $\underline{u}_o$, $\dot{\underline{u}}_o$ we need about 55 op.
- 2.2. For deriving $\bar{\underline{u}}$, we need another 35 op.
- 2.3. Deriving $\sin \bar{\alpha}$, $\cos \bar{\alpha}$, $\sin \bar{\delta}$, $\cos \bar{\delta}$, $\sec^2 \bar{\rho}$, $\sin \bar{U}$, $\cos \bar{U}$ from $\bar{\underline{u}}$ requires about 20 op.
- 2.4. Computation of $A^{(1)} - A^{(5)}$ now takes 30 op.
- 2.5. The global distortion (instrument plus light-deflection) is not yet finally parametrized. From Cowling's thesis (pp 91-96) it appears that, for a fairly general cylindrical metric, the deflection can be

given as a function of three angles. (β_p, η_p) give the RGC pole coordinates relative to the sun, and ψ is simply the abscissa difference relative to the sun ($v - v_s$). For the low amplitudes expected, it is sufficient to calculate β_p, η_p and v_s for the mean time of each set only (in RGC-file?). The important variable is ψ , and $\cos \psi, \sin \psi$ can be derived in 6 op. Cowling identifies 8-12 global parameters (combinations of space-time metric coefficients), but with rather complicated expressions for $G^{(k)}$ requiring some 300-400 op in all. The thermal effects that may distort the instrument should depend also mainly on the angle ψ . A minimum set of global parameters should be the 12 harmonic coefficients in ψ (to order 6). To compute these coefficients from $\cos \psi, \sin \psi$ takes about 50 op.

- 2.6. To compute the rhs, we need only v^{comp} , as v^{obs} is that given by the set solution. From $\sin \bar{v}, \cos \bar{v}$ we obtain $\bar{v}$ in about 20 op. The correction Δv^{glob} is linear in the $G^{(k)}$ -coefficients and takes at most about 40 op.

In total, this gives some 250-650 op per observation equation, depending on the number and form of the global parameters.

3. Formation of the normal equations

The fundamental document for the accumulation of the normal equations (including preadjustment and elimination of the astrometric parameters) is Table 1 in WP7100 (NDAC/LO/022). The main part of the reduced normals is the dense (NSETOR, NSETOR)-matrix $\underline{D}$. For the full mission, NSETOR $\approx$ 2000, and $\underline{D}$ has thus some $2 \cdot 10^6$ elements. The accumulation can not be done in a single pass through Table 1, and an important question is whether some data should be stored for reuse during each of several tens of passes.

A closer scrutiny of Table 1 identifies three major computational tasks:

- (1) The computation of $\underline{A}, \underline{G}, h$ as outlined in Section 2.
- (2) The MESH procedure for eliminating slit errors (G K Andreasen, 1983 July 1).
- (3) The accumulation of $\underline{D}$.

Once performed on a certain star, the MESH procedure need not be repeated.

Also, the matrices $\underline{E}$, $\underline{e}$, $\underline{F}$ and $\underline{f}$ have a total number of components $\sim \text{NGLOB} \times 2000$, which is well within the main memory capacity. Consequently, we may envisage a first pass through Table 1 where these matrices are accumulated, and the star positions are updated through MESH and ADJUST. The order of magnitude estimate for the amount of computation can be set at $(1-2) 10^5$ op per star (with about half spent by MESH). After this first pass we have to make some tens of passes to accumulate $\underline{D}$. This matrix does not involve the global parameters, and we may consider storing the $\underline{A}^{(k)}$ -values from pass 1. As seen from Table 1, however, what is really used is the Cholesky-reduced vector $\underline{\tilde{H}}$, one for each set and each star. With all these $\underline{\tilde{H}}$ -vectors stored, each extra pass through Table 1 would involve some 8000 op per star. With no storage, we would have about the double. The decision depends on the actual hardware performance and on the number of blocks (extra passes) in the normal equations. The first pass through Table 1 is probably dominant, and the gain in computation time with storage may well be offset by the extra disk access time for retrieving some 100 Mb of data.

4. Solution of the normal equations

The normal equations finally accumulated (as described in Section 3) are now solved for the corrections to the ≈ 2000 set zero points and the (10-30?) global parameters. Because the equations have a rank deficiency of 6, the pseudo-solution given in WP6100 and NDAC/LO/018 is used. The modifications are minor with respect to computing time, and the solution can be obtained in a few times 10^9 op.

With adjustments on the order of arcseconds or less, the observation equations for Step 2/3 can probably be considered linear. The solution will not have to be iterated because of non-linearity in the coefficients, but only because of a changed selection of observations or weights.

The major part of the Step 2/3-process is thus the accumulation of the normals. Because of this dominance, it is important that all possible global terms are included in the observation equations. Their *a priori* values may be conveniently set to zero, and thus $\Delta U^{\text{glob}} = 0$ in the computations of the rhs. For the solution, we may then select some subset of the globals to be included, and the rows and columns in the NE corresponding to the unused ones are simply deleted. Several such solutions can be made, and a number of "significant" global parameters singled out. One should

note, however, that the preadjustment of the astrometric parameters assumes $\Delta g \approx 0$. If non-zero values are found for some global parameters, these values have to be applied in calculating the rhs in future iterations, and the corresponding terms may not be deleted (without recalculating the rhs).

5. The work file

An important concept in the practical Step 1 solution process is the "work-file". This includes all input and output, and a work-file is thus a self-contained unit ready for processing. A work-file for the Step 2/3-process can be similarly defined, but the large amounts of data involved make it less useful. In Step 1, work-files are created and processed more or less automatically by the data management system (C Petersen, 1983 July 28). In Step 2/3, each solution process is initiated individually, and it should not be necessary to store a work-file for later re-processing.

The work-file concept may thus be superfluous in practice, but it is useful for displaying the data files involved in the processing. Fig. 1 is a schematic representation of a "work-file" for Step 2/3. The approximate sizes of the sub-files (for the full mission) are given, and the DID:s are indicated. The total size of such a work-file is then some 330 Mb with storage of the A-coefficients, 250 Mb without.

6. Conclusions

The final Step 2/3-process is a large task, that may require several days of computer time for each iteration. The results of the processing are the final HIPPARCOS results, however, and it is imperative that all the programs involved work correctly. As far as possible, the programs for Step 1 should be used in Step 2/3 also, but there are certainly differences that must be allowed for.

The question whether to store intermediate observation equation data for the NE accumulation has to be answered by practical tests of computing times. Also, the "work-file" concept may or may not be needed. As for the details of the processing, many more points have to be cleared up. There are unsolved problems regarding e.g. the global parametrization, the rejection of double stars or the calculation of ephemerides.

INPUT	WORK FILE	OUTPUT
	<u>Star-catalogue:</u> 11.6 Mb (116 bytes/star)	
DID35	ID(4), VR(4) BMAG(4), BMV(4) RA(8), DEC(8), PMRA(4) PMDEC(4), PX(4), MULT(4) NOBS(4), GOF3(4) COVAST(15×4)	) DID37
	<u>Auxiliary Star-catalogue:</u> 3.2 Mb (32 bytes/star)	
	RA(8), DEC(8), PMRA(4) PMDEC(4), PX(4), $\Pi v_R R^{-1}(4)$	
	<u>RGC-file:</u> 0.2 Mb (116 bytes/set)	
	ISET(4), CSET(8) RASET(8), DECSET(8)	) DID36
	$\sin \alpha_R(8), \cos \alpha_R(8)$ $\sin \delta_R(8), \cos \delta_R(8)$ $\sin \alpha_R \sin \delta_R(8), \sin \alpha_R \cos \delta_R(8)$ $\cos \alpha_R \sin \delta_R(8), \cos \alpha_R \cos \delta_R(8)$ $\sin \beta_p(4), \sin \eta_p(4), \sin v_G(4)$ $\cos \beta_p(4), \cos \eta_p(4), \cos v_G(4)$	
	<u>Ephemeris-file:</u> < 0.5 Mb	
DID34	Chebyshev-coeff for ROBS, RSUN	
	<u>Aux:</u> < 0.1 Mb Global parameters, datamatic parameters	
	<u>Observations:</u> 160 Mb (40 bytes/obs)	
DID33	ABSC(8), GOF(4), ABSCPG(4) ISET(4), TOBS(8), SDABSC(4) RES3(4), WEIGHT(4)	) DID37
	<u>Obs eq for double stars:</u> 50 Mb (64 bytes/obs)	
	$\underline{A}(5 \times 4), \underline{G}(10 \times 4), \text{rhs}(4)$	) DID38
	<u>Obs eq for NE accumulation:</u> 80 Mb (20 bytes/obs)	
	$\tilde{H}(5 \times 4)$	
	<u>Normal equations:</u> 16 Mb (2 10 ⁶ coeff REAL*8)	

FIGURE 1. The "work-file" for Step 2/3. Figures in parentheses are the number of bytes required for each variable.